

Experiences in Protecting Socioeconomic Life During the War on Gaza

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Abstract

This paper presents a Gazan researcher personal experiences in protecting elements of the social economy in his surroundings during more than 18 months of aggression on Gaza. The study emphasises that efforts to sustain life must continue as part of the resilience process, especially since Palestinians in Gaza have nothing left to lose. Poverty rates have exceeded 80%, according to UNRWA statistics from August 2023, while extreme poverty—including food insecurity—has risen to 60%, according to the same source. This is a result of one of the harshest blockades in the world imposed on Palestine, particularly the Gaza Strip—an economic and financial blockade, restrictions on movement and trade, and a ban on travel for medical treatment or tourism .

The paper focuses on analysing the unconventional mechanisms devised by some Palestinians to sustain economic life despite the destruction of infrastructure and severe Israeli restrictions on imports and exports. These mechanisms include the parallel economy, resource recycling, community solidarity, and creative economy. The study also demonstrates how persistent individual efforts to resist can help mitigate the impact of the economic and trade blockade, even if only slightly alleviating the complete stagnation in import and export processes. Israeli approvals have imposed hundreds of restrictions on imports, effectively banning most goods that support industry, agriculture, fishing, and construction. This is in addition to the financial, health, psychological, and educational blockades. The study concludes with the hope that Palestinians will continue to reinforce the foundations of life in Gaza through innovative efforts, no matter how long the siege and war persist.

Keywords: Socioeconomy, Gaza, Palestine, War Economy, Economic Experiences for Sustaining Life, Resilience in Gaza.

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1.0 Introduction

This paper reviews field experiences in confronting the collapse of the socio-economic situation in the Gaza Strip during the war that began in October 2023, which followed 18 months of escalating Israeli blockade (Migdad et al., 2024a). The study aims to document individual and community resilience strategies that contributed to mitigating the effects of the comprehensive blockade, which has reduced more than 80% of the population to poverty, according to UNRWA statistics (2023), while 60% suffer from food insecurity.

The paper focuses on analysing the unconventional mechanisms Palestinians have devised to maintain economic life despite the destruction of infrastructure and the imposition of severe Israeli restrictions on imports and exports, including:

1. The parallel economy (such as the black market).
2. Resource recycling (converting tents into workshops, using cooking oil as fuel).
3. Community solidarity (hospitals, family coordination to manage scarce resources).
4. The creative economy (textile projects, mobile vending, waste reuse).

Migdad et al. (2024b), Buheji and Hasan (2024a)

The paper also discusses the failure of international institutions to meet basic needs due to Israeli restrictions, and recommends the development of flexible, self-sufficient economic models, along with international pressure to break the blockade.

2.0 Literature Review

2.1 The War Economy

A war economy is an economic system reshaped to meet the demands of armed conflict that may occur in any unstable country or region, whether through the mobilisation of resources for military efforts or through informal coping mechanisms that allow civilians to survive in the shadow of destruction. The war economy is divided into the "traditional war economy," which is controlled by the state through policies such as military financing, military manufacturing, and conscription (as in World War II). There is also the "informal war economy," which emerges in areas where the state is weak and relies on the black market, smuggling, and the parallel economy (such as Syria, Yemen, and Gaza). Poast (2005)

War economies address the challenges of systematic destruction, whereby the aggressor attempts to destroy the enemy's infrastructure to weaken its adversary's economic capacity (such as bombing factories and ports in Gaza). They also tighten the economic

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blockade to restrict the movement of goods and capital (e.g., the ban on the entry of construction materials into Gaza since 2007). They also prevent the spread of a parallel economy based on the proliferation of materials that sustain resilience through the black market to compensate for shortages (such as food, fuel, or medicine being sold at exorbitant prices). Buheji (2025), Migdad et al. (2024b)

Smuggling is also one of the mechanisms of the war economy. Therefore, it is natural to see tunnels in Gaza, or to rely on airlifts as an alternative to closed crossings. These economies also rely on the transfer of resources through the reuse of waste or available materials (such as converting cooking oil into car fuel or using all types of textiles for clothing, blankets, or other materials).

2.2 Types of Restrictions in the War Economy in Gaza

The Zionist occupation has attempted to innovate in imposing restrictions and restrictions on all aspects of life, starting with the availability of water, food, and even a healthy environment (Al-Muhannadi and Buheji, 2024). It has done so by imposing hundreds of import restrictions, preventing most imports that stimulate industry, agriculture, fishing, and the construction sector. This repression has been reinforced by restrictions reflected in the financial, health, psychological, and educational blockade (Shorrab et al., 2024), and even in the areas of electricity, sanitation, and everything else that could ensure a decent life for Palestinians in Gaza. Regarding movement and travel, whether for medical treatment, trade, or tourism, the occupation has made it difficult for Palestinians, especially in Gaza.

The people of Gaza have gone through multiple stages of travel difficulties, sometimes reaching a complete ban for months at a time for all categories. When permitted to travel, those wishing to travel must wait for months until their turn arrives, until they pay thousands of dollars for travel for themselves and their families, up to \$50,000. In addition, tens of thousands of Palestinians are completely banned from travelling, not only through the Erez crossing but also through the Salah al-Din crossing between Gaza and Egypt. The Sabah al-Din crossing is viewed as a Palestinian-Egyptian crossing, and officially it is. However, ongoing Israeli intervention has turned the crossing into a large prison and a major extortion station for Palestinians, whether as a passenger crossing or for transporting goods. This has led to the unfair and unacceptable absorption of Palestinian liquidity through bribes, exorbitant transportation fees, and the allocation of turns for trucks, in addition to obstruction, delays, and the payment of waiting fees, among other things. There were also restrictions on the travel of patients and the injured to receive treatment abroad. Israeli refusal and restrictions on their travel often led to the indirect killing of patients due to the lack of appropriate treatment and medical equipment, particularly for cancer and chronic diseases.

The situation did not stop there, but extended to direct killing by bullets and the bombing of homes and civilians. Thousands of Palestinians were killed before October 7, 2023. This was in addition to the policy of humiliation and domination practised by the Israeli occupation against Palestinians and Palestinian leaders in general. This was in addition to the ongoing attacks on the Palestinian people in Jerusalem, Al-Aqsa Mosque, and other areas of the West Bank, which made life in the West Bank and Jerusalem nearly impossible for Palestinians, who suffer from the fragmentation of areas in Jerusalem and the Safa and the difficulty of accessing one place to another.

All of the above, coupled with the Palestinians' frustration with any political solution, Israel's procrastination in implementing the two-state solution, and the categorical rejection of the two-state solution by many Israeli officials, contributed to the Palestinian initiative in the events of October 7, 2023.

2.3 The Surprise Attack (Operation Al-Aqsa Flood) October 7, 2023

The Al-Aqsa Flood War, as Hamas calls it, began after a coordinated and surprise attack launched by Hamas against Israel on the morning of Saturday, in response to the ongoing Israeli attacks against the Palestinian people. Thousands of Palestinian militants launched rockets from the Hamas-ruled Gaza Strip toward Israel. In addition, thousands of Palestinian militants entered the Gaza Strip and other towns adjacent to the Strip, known as the Gaza Envelope. They seized control of several military sites, particularly in Sderot, Afukim, and Netivot, and engaged in violent clashes in the three settlements and elsewhere. They also captured a large number of soldiers and civilians, taking them to Gaza, in addition to seizing several Israeli military vehicles. The attack led to the deaths of approximately 1,500 Israelis at the start of the battle, and the capture of approximately 250 others, according to the Israeli press. Not only did armed Palestinian factions enter the Gaza Strip, but thousands of civilians also entered the towns by various means after the borders were opened and armed factions entered. We saw with our own eyes civilians seizing some of the goods from these towns, claiming that they were Palestinian territories occupied by Israel and that they and what was in them belonged to the Palestinians. Buheji (2024a)

The attack took Israel by surprise, despite the confirmed warnings from Egyptian and Saudi intelligence to their Israeli counterparts, who did not take the warning seriously at all. Saudi Arabia linked its warning to an imminent explosion in the Palestinian territories due to the continued occupation and the lack of a political horizon.

The surprise came because Hamas and its Qassam Brigades employed sophisticated and deceptive tactics, making it appear that any actions were merely training. This was in addition to the movement's repeated indications that it was primarily concerned with governance, internal politics, and providing job opportunities, especially within the

occupied territories. Furthermore, its failure to contribute to the response to the assassination of Islamic Jihad leaders made it appear complacent and complacent, seeking an economic solution to the crises in the Gaza Strip it controls. The Strip is suffering from difficulties in every area due to the blockade, Israeli intransigence, and the massive extortion by the Sons of Sinai Company, which is working to drain Gaza of liquidity and continue to impoverish it in a blatant and unjust manner. Migdad and Buheji (2024a)

2.4 The Unexpected War

Although approximately 44 countries condemned Hamas's attack on the Gaza Strip towns, the brutality and severity of the Israeli assault on everything in Gaza, from stones and trees to children and women, and the escalation of the killings have led to a rise in the death toll to 36,439 martyrs, 82,627 injuries, and 10,000 missing under the rubble since last October 7, according to Ma'an News Agency. All of this has led most countries around the world to condemn this Israeli attack on civilians and the level of killing and destruction of all aspects of life. Many have even suspected that this war was planned, regardless of the October 7 attack, and aimed at forcibly or voluntarily displacing Palestinians under the pretext of eliminating Hamas. Much evidence points in this direction. Buheji and Migdad (2025b)

The "War of Swords" (as Israel calls it) began on the same day as the Flood and continued for approximately eight months, as of the date of this writing, with massive killing and destruction of everything. Israel categorically rejected all calls to stop the war and implement a prisoner exchange deal, despite the existence of American and international initiatives that Hamas accepted. However, Israel has always rejected these deals.

3.0 Socioeconomic Observations of Life in Gaza Under the War

This section is dedicated to the various repercussions and types of socioeconomic resilience of the people of Gaza as experienced and observed by the first author.

3.1 The State of the Socio-Economic Environment in Gaza Under the War

How can we talk about a social economy exhausted by a twenty-year blockade, recurring wars every two years, and then a brutal war in October 2023 that destroyed everything, leaving no human being or stone untouched? We are talking about an economy whose human resources were wounded and killed, amounting to approximately 200,000 people, representing approximately 10% of the population, in a very small area of approximately 360 square kilometres. Migdad et al. (2024a)

Before October 7, the poverty rate exceeded 80%, food insecurity exceeded 60%, and unemployment was also high. After the war, life ceased to exist, as the entire population was displaced, either within the governorates, between governorates, or migrating abroad (Buheji and Migdad, 2025a). Factories, farms, shops, infrastructure, roads, bridges,

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internet and communication networks, electricity, water, and even sewage systems were destroyed. Commercial life came to a complete standstill, and crossings were closed, except for aid deliveries, forcing all people to rely on aid, if it was available. The education and health systems were also completely destroyed, with schools and hospitals destroyed and scientists and doctors killed in the Gaza Strip.

People were displaced from their homes under bombardment and unable to carry their belongings, leaving them in desperate need of everything. They carried with them their cash (if they had any), which had been depleted during the eight months of war. Most salaries were halted and replaced with small, intermittent loans, if available. Most people relied on the aid that arrived intermittently and without regularization. Most of it even reached the markets and was sold at high prices.

Most people lived in tents. Buildings were destroyed, and those that remained were rented out to their owners at prices up to ten times their normal price. There was no water, gas, or electricity in the tents. Cooking was done with firewood, and water was consumed in buckets. Fuel was scarce. The price of a kilo of cooking gas reached 100 shekels, and a litre of gasoline cost more than \$25. A kilo of firewood costs 4 shekels, more than a dollar, ten times its normal price. Migdad et al. (2024a)

However, commodity prices remained extremely high, orders were virtually nonexistent, security was weak, and the availability of goods was so scarce that famine was rife in Gaza City and the north. The price of a 25-kilogram bag of flour reached nearly \$1,000. All of this was due to Israeli policies aimed at spreading chaos to hasten the end of Hamas rule in the Gaza Strip. Therefore, Israel bombed any entity working to organise, protect security, peace, or organise the distribution of aid. Several Palestinian police units were repeatedly bombed while securing aid convoys arriving from the crossings for UNRWA. Hassoun et al (2024).

All of the above have led to a deteriorating economic situation, the deterioration of all sectors, and the lack of job opportunities, given the displacement of the entire population of the Gaza Strip after ten months of war. It has also led to the entire population's dependence on aid, which does not reach everyone, is not delivered fairly, and much of it is stolen and sold in markets to displaced people whose funds have run out over time. This has led to their collapse, impoverishment, and living below the poverty line, even extreme poverty, with food insecurity, the spread of chaos and lawlessness, and aid-stealing gangs. Buheji and Migdad (2025a)

3.2 Socioeconomic Opportunities During the War on Gaza

With the lack of traditional job opportunities and the displaced people's need for money to provide a minimum standard of living, some businesses have proliferated that provide a few job opportunities with minimal financial returns. These include working in street

vendors, most of whom sell aid, whether stolen or obtained by the citizen in excess of their needs, along with some goods purchased from merchants. These stalls also sell vegetables and fruits, which are available depending on the availability of goods. These stalls often cease operations and rarely generate sufficient income for a living. Buheji and Mushimiyimana (2024)

Gazans have developed a culture of problem-solving, and businesses related to the war economy have proliferated, fulfilling the requirements of the social economy (Migdad et al., 2024a). For example, the services of erecting tents and pergolas, constructing bathrooms, and digging wells for them have become widespread, especially since these services are of utmost importance to the displaced people living in tents, given the lack of digging tools and bathroom materials, such as wood and tarpaulins. The queue functioned as a queue, and there are many examples of this, including: a queue at the bakery to buy a loaf of bread and resell it, thus providing a financial return in exchange for the time spent in line, and a similar queue to buy a carton of eggs and resell them, or anything of a similar nature. Of course, all of this occurred while the monetary blockade and the closure of banks continued, providing job opportunities for those queuing at bank ATMs, as an individual might need to wait a day, a night, or more to withdraw 1,000 shekels from his bank account, which led some to buy queues for 50 or 100 shekels, equivalent to \$15-30 (Migdad et al. (2024a)).

Gangs that steal aid trucks have also spread, and they are often composed of large families living in marginalised areas. Unfortunately, these families have exploited the security vacuum to carry out this suspicious role, along with their family members. The business of traditional formal traders also declined, while the business of warlords, monopolists, and exploiters expanded, taking over from other formal traders who were unable to operate in the security vacuum, anarchy, and weak rule of law.

Tekiyas, which sprang up during the war to provide food to the displaced, typically employ 10-20 workers. Some individuals also engaged in other similar activities, such as distributing and selling tea, coffee, ice cream, and cold water, or selling sandwiches, barbecued meats, and other items. Some began working with charitable and relief organisations on a temporary basis for varying periods, averaging around three months, with a limited salary barely enough to support a family, around \$11 per day. Hassoun et al (2025).

Some Gazans also established primitive cafes that provide coffee, internet, and suitable seating for those in need, as people were displaced in hellishly hot tents with no place to sit or use the internet (Buheji and Migdad, 2025a). New means of transportation were also devised in the face of fuel scarcity. Carts pulled by horses or donkeys became widespread, and cars replaced diesel with cooking oil as fuel, with trailers added to the vehicles to accommodate the largest possible number of passengers. Trucks, which had

no other job opportunities, also provided income for their owners. Many individual businesses also provided dozens of opportunities, such as money exchange and money transfers, where commission rates reached over 20% simply for bringing money into the Gaza Strip from abroad.

3.3 The Socioeconomic Perspective of the Land, Air, and Sea Aid

Before the war, Gaza was heavily dependent on aid, with approximately 70% of the population receiving aid. This continued after the war, but more clearly and comprehensively, encompassing all Gazans. The displacement levelled down, and almost everyone became destitute and in need of aid, with no distinction between rich and poor, citizen and refugee.

UNRWA and some international organisations, thankfully, brought in hundreds of trucks of aid daily. However, this aid was marred by a lack of order and poor coordination between the agencies delivering aid, as well as between these agencies and the security and police protection agencies. This led to the theft of much of this aid and its diversion for sale on the black market, which became widespread during the war. The lack of organisation also led to the inconsistent entry of goods and aid, which contributed to malnutrition. For example, large quantities of flour entered the Strip, many times the amount needed, while meat or chicken, for example, did not enter. This led to a major imbalance in the pricing system for goods and the prices of aid items needed by citizens.

This aid enters through the Kerem Shalom crossing and the Rafah commercial crossing. With the Israeli restrictions on these crossings, and with hundreds of trucks piling up on the Egyptian side awaiting Israeli inspection at the Auja (Nitsana) crossing, where they wait for days for inspection before being able to enter, and with much of the aid being spoiled, some countries began to rely on airlifts of aid. Migdad and Buheji (2024b)

2.4 The Effectiveness of Airlifts and Their Impact on the Socio-Economic Sector

Many countries, such as Egypt, Jordan, the UAE, and some European countries, have pioneered the method of airdropping aid to besieged areas, both in the north and the south. While this aid has provided some of the necessary supplies to the besieged Gaza Strip, it has many drawbacks. Briefly, it can be said that this aid was in very small quantities and distributed in a chaotic, haphazard manner. It led to numerous massacres among the needy population waiting for it, such as the flour massacre at the Netzarim checkpoint, where much of the aid was dropped in the vicinity of tanks, which carried out more than one massacre against these poor residents. Buheji (2024b)

In many cases, the umbrellas for the aid boxes failed to open, causing them to fall on homes and people, partially destroying some homes and killing some residents. The first author witnessed and experienced this with his uncles' homes, where the roofs were destroyed in the northern Gaza Strip. It was also clear that this type of aid would not last

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long, as the cost of transporting it is prohibitive compared to land transportation via the Rafah border crossing between Egypt and Palestine.

The controversial US floating port was built in the Netzarim axis. Controversy has raged over its purpose: was it to seize Gaza's gas, to voluntarily displace Gazans to alleviate the embarrassment of Egypt, or to bring in aid? According to Channel 12, Washington is considering using helicopters to deliver aid to Gaza after the failure of the \$320 million floating port. Controversy has also raged over its ownership and management: whether it will be American, Israeli, or transferred to the Palestinians after the war on Gaza ends and a different entity assumes control. In any case, the port's construction appears to have been poor and primitive, to the point that wind and slight waves caused its pieces to scatter, prompting its management to temporarily move it to the Israeli port of Ashdod pending repairs. Overall, some aid has been brought into Gaza through this port. It can be argued that the Egyptian-Palestinian crossing would have been sufficient for aid if Egypt had exercised its sovereignty over the crossing and allowed the entry of all aid without delays that would lead to its spoilage, regardless of Israel's desire to obstruct or prevent it. Migdad et al. (2025)

3.4 Emphasising the Socioeconomic Stability Role of the UNRWA

UNRWA is considered the primary international organisation providing relief and works for Palestinian refugees in Palestine and the diaspora. Part of its existence is seen as politically linked to the Palestinian issue, and its existence will continue as long as Palestinian refugees exist. Accordingly, Israel views it with suspicion, mistrust, and even hostility. Therefore, in this war, we have seen an Israeli tendency to marginalise and even eliminate the agency's role and replace it with roles specific to other international institutions. This has been rejected by the agency and by the Palestinian government, both in Gaza and the West Bank. Accordingly, the role of UNRWA must be strengthened, and alternative roles for any other international organisation must be rejected, while accepting its continued role as a supporter and complement to UNRWA's role, not as a substitute for it.

4.0 Socioeconomic Experiences During the Gaza War

In the following examples, the first author shares his own family experience and experimentation to sustain their life in Gaza and keep their resilience.

4.1 The Weavers – The Al-Maqdad Family and Their Displaced People

The Al-Aqsa Flood War of October 7, 2023, led to the displacement of hundreds of thousands of Palestinian families from the northern Gaza Strip to its southern part. Our home in Rafah was home to at least 100 displaced people. The family home in Rafah was also home to over 300 displaced people. The days passed, and the children and women began to feel empty, bored, and extremely afraid. They had exhausted themselves and tried some traditional games, including cards, chess, Monopoly, hopscotch, hide-and-

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seek, and others. As winter approached its peak, everyone realised their need for some wool items, so they suggested the idea of weaving wool to make some items that would keep them warm. And so it was.

The first author's granddaughter, Lian, had tried to learn weaving long ago, but was unable to do so due to her lack of patience and the many alternatives available to make the most of her time. However, with no other alternatives available, she tried again during the war. Her grandmother had doubts about her success in weaving, but surprisingly, she learned and succeeded with distinction, producing numerous pieces and becoming her grandmother's foremost competitor in the speed and quality of her woollen weaving. In fact, a number of the woollen pieces she wove travelled across the borders to the United States, Turkey, and other countries, confirming the potential for developing this idea into an income-generating business for the family and those working with her. Buheji et al (2024).

The house became a textile factory run by the grandmother, where her daughters, granddaughters, and a number of displaced people worked. They worked like a beehive, all competing to make woollen pieces to protect themselves from the cold. Among the products she made were scarves, hats, cuffs, wallets, and more.

4.2 Stalls and New Traders

The above discussion concerned women and girls. Boys, however, turned to trade, learning the basics and rules of commerce and becoming business owners. Some sold vegetables, others sold biscuits, some sold ghariba, and some ran stalls selling a variety of food and canned goods. These activities had a positive impact on the children, refining their knowledge and shaping their personalities. They helped support families and helped them acquire life skills and experiences, among other things. The researcher was personally surprised by the children's talents in managing their businesses and their ability to keep up with the market and deal with customers, noting that the oldest of these children was no more than 14 years old. They practised the profession through both success and failure, and changed the scope of their work through failure and expanded it through success. For them, it was a pioneering experience and practical learning in the field of commerce and business. Buheji and Migdad (2025b); Migdad et al. (2024c).

4.3 Al-Miqdad Bakery for Pastries and Baked Goods

When the first author's family were displaced to Rafah, he found his brothers sitting at home, not working, even though they were business owners and furniture traders. This was due to the fear of war. Thus, the family began to move towards trade, hoping to motivate and assist his brothers in alleviating their fear and encouraging them to work. The researcher's brother also started some businesses, including selling falafel, vegetables, and canned goods. Some of these experiences were successful, while others were not.

However, with repeated attempts, he was able to achieve stability in work, especially in the field of trade.

He would buy large quantities of supplies from wholesalers and then sell them wholesale to other traders, making some profits that helped him pay off a significant portion of his debt, as well as support his family. The researcher's younger brother's idea was to sell pastries and sweets. He, his wife, sons, and daughters began making pastries and selling them to people in small quantities due to the scarcity of basic pastry ingredients. Over time, pastry ingredients became available, but they were expensive, which presented one of the challenges he faced and overcame through his problem-solving mindset. He expanded the project to become a source of livelihood for more than 20 family members and some displaced people with baking experience. He made numerous improvements to the bakery, including tools and equipment, and developed his business in a new way, especially for the holy month of Ramadan. Al-Muhannadi and Buheji (2024)

The bakery's experience was very successful and may continue beyond the war. It may even have prompted Mr. Nabil to change his profession from carpentry to pastry making.

4.4 Layan Clothing Showroom

The son of the first author had a clothing showroom in Nuseirat, opposite the Al-Qassam Mosque. It contained over \$120,000 worth of clothing for approximately 20 shareholders in the company. After we were displaced to Rafah, and thus the showroom was feared of it being bombed, thus he moved the showroom to Rafah.

Moving the showroom and selling clothes was a very unique experience, with significant benefits, including saving the family's and partners' money from destruction. The family members gained experience in selling and working in the showroom, as they had no such experience. They learned not only sales methods but also how to deal with people.

Layan distributed some of the clothes from the showroom to displaced people as part of charitable efforts. Layan and his family were able to raise some funding from abroad to support the poor and needy among the displaced people with some clothing, as they had left their homes, fleeing killing and death, without taking any of their belongings, which increased their need and poverty.

Most of the family's livelihood during the war, had changed. Especially those working in the government or who depended on salaries. Many of them didn't receive salaries for over twenty-two months. This made the financial situation difficult; thus, trading in the sale of clothing is not an easy job, as it is considered to be a luxury product in times of war.

The work in the clothing store opened up opportunities for the family to trade in other areas, which provided real financial benefits on the one hand, and provided necessities for the camp on the other. The family extended their trading in flour, cola, food supplies, and clothing imported from Egypt.

All the family members kept themselves busy managing the exhibition, which relieved them from emptiness, boredom, fear, and thoughts of the horrors and darkness of war. The family were able to return the money of our partners and shareholders amidst this destructive war.

4.5 Al-Miqdad Family Community Kitchen (Tekiyas)

A Tekiya is a place where food is prepared with charitable, self-financing, or joint funding and distributed to people in need free of charge. There are many charitable people open to the idea of feeding and donating to people, but finding an intermediary who can transfer their money to charitable causes is difficult. Therefore, we contacted numerous charitable people, some of whom were willing to support displaced families financially, through food parcels, or meals. This is where the idea of establishing the Al-Miqdad Tekia began.

The Al-Miqdad Tekia began operating, providing intermittent meals based on the support and funding it received. The Tekia faced many difficulties in light of the siege imposed on the Gaza Strip, the brutal war, and the scarcity of basic food supplies. Communication was not limited to charitable people alone. We also contacted foreign organisations such as WCK and UNRWA, and an agreement was reached to establish a fully equipped kitchen capable of feeding 500 displaced families (approximately 2,000 people, most of whom are displaced). We donated a dedicated space for the kitchen, a 400-square-meter barn owned by the family. The establishment of the kitchen had numerous benefits for all parties involved. Twenty-two unemployed individuals were officially employed under UNRWA's temporary employment program, all of whom were in need, most of them family members, relatives, and women. A daily meal was also provided to all displaced families, neighbours, and needy displaced persons, alleviating their financial burdens.

The hospice also provides intermittent dinners, depending on the availability of food supplies. WCK provided us with all necessary kitchen supplies, including large stoves, wood stoves, and saj ovens. It also provided us with food, fuel, water, solar panels, and other supplies. Buheji et al (2024).

4.6 General Trade

The exorbitant inflation and skyrocketing prices that have swept the markets have made everyone in need of money, which has pushed everyone who can work in trade to work in it. Indeed, we were able to establish a store to trade all types of goods, depending on

availability. We traded in imported clothes from Egypt, as well as various types of juices, flour, vegetables, eggs, chicken, meat, and more.

We faced a significant problem related to the significant increase in prices. Perhaps the most important reason for this was the high transportation costs in Egypt via the Sons of Sinai Company, in addition to the unethical monopoly of a number of merchants. The Israeli occupation only allowed five companies to import, which strengthened the monopoly and perpetuated unprecedented price increases. The occupation's ban on the import of most goods further exacerbated and intensified the problem.

5.0 Conclusion

5.1 Learning and Reflections Based on the Experiences of Trying to Socioeconomically Survive during the War

The learning from this case lead us to start first by acknowledging the remarkable ability of the Palestinians in Gaza to adapt under the most difficult circumstances, not only to survive, but also to create a suitable business environment that enables them to cover their general living expenses. This was evident in the actions of the mother, daughter, and son, as well as the primary behaviour of the head of the household, who, along with the family, endeavoured in every way to facilitate their living conditions, devising ways to provide a living wage and inspiring work under the harsh conditions. This enabled them to remain steadfast on the Palestinian land of Gaza and to reject voluntary or forced displacement to any other country in the world, regardless of the difficult circumstances and harsh living conditions.

5.2 Mitigating the Spillovers of the Total Socioeconomic Collapse

The socio-economic collapse in Gaza following the October 2023 war has forced Palestinians to adopt extraordinary survival mechanisms. The study highlights how informal economies, community solidarity, and creative resource management have become essential in mitigating the effects of Israel's blockade and widespread destruction. These adaptive strategies—ranging from black markets to makeshift workshops—demonstrate the resilience of Gaza's population despite systemic oppression and scarcity.

The failure of international institutions to provide adequate aid underscores the necessity for self-sufficient economic models. While UNRWA remains a critical lifeline, its limitations amid Israeli restrictions reveal the urgent need for alternative, decentralised support systems. The rise of grassroots initiatives, such as community kitchens (Tekiyas) and small-scale trade, illustrates how localised efforts can sustain livelihoods when formal structures collapse. However, these solutions are temporary and fragile, heavily dependent on external funding and unstable supply chains.

5.3 What the War Economy Exposed?

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The war economy in Gaza has also exposed deep structural vulnerabilities. The blockade's chokehold on imports, particularly food, fuel, and medical supplies, has forced Palestinians into exploitative black markets, where prices are inflated and access is unequal. Smuggling and resource recycling, though innovative, are unsustainable long-term strategies. Moreover, the targeting of civil infrastructure (hospitals, schools, police) has exacerbated chaos, making even basic governance nearly impossible.

The study also raises critical questions about the role of international aid. While airdrops and maritime corridors have provided some relief, their inefficiency and high costs highlight the need for unrestricted land access through Egypt and Israel. The politicisation of aid, where Israel controls and often obstructs humanitarian shipments, further complicates recovery efforts.

The Gaza Strip's socio-economic collapse under war and blockade has necessitated unprecedented levels of resilience. Palestinians have adapted through informal economies, communal support, and inventive survival tactics, yet these measures are stopgaps rather than sustainable solutions. The international community's failure to enforce humanitarian access or pressure Israel to lift restrictions has perpetuated suffering, pushing Gaza deeper into poverty and dependency.

5.4 Lessons for Meaningful Socioeconomic Recovery

For meaningful recovery, besides lifting the blockage, Gaza requires unrestricted access to trade, reconstruction materials, and essential goods is non-negotiable for economic revival. Supporting small businesses, cooperatives, and grassroots initiatives can also foster Gaza's self-reliance and Gazans's proven that they are capable of managing it themselves. Therefore, International agencies must bypass Israeli obstruction by establishing direct, unimpeded supply routes.

Without systemic change, Gaza's resilience will remain a story of survival under oppression rather than a pathway to genuine recovery. The international community must move beyond symbolic gestures and demand structural solutions that restore dignity, autonomy, and economic viability to Palestinians in Gaza.

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